

Modern Friedel-Crafts chemistry. Part-29. Cyclialkylation of some triphenylated propane, butane and pentane substrates to diphenylated indans under Friedel-Crafts conditions

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Abstract : Reactions under Friedel-Crafts cyclialkylation conditions produced : isomeric 1,2-diphenylindans from 1,2,3-triphenyl-(1- or 2-)propanol and 1-chloro-2,3,3-triphenylpropane, *trans*-2-benzyl-1-phenylindan from 2-benzyl-1,3-diphenyl-2-propanol, isomeric 1-methyl-1,2-diphenylindans from 2,3,4-triphenyl-2-butanol, 1,1-dimethyl-3,4-diphenylindan from 2-methyl-3,4,4-triphenyl-2-butanol, and isomeric 1-ethyl-1,3-diphenylindans from 1,1,3-triphenyl-3-pentanol. Mechanistic interpretations and product identifications are offered.

Keywords : Cyclialkylation, Friedel-Crafts conditions, triphenylated alkane substrates, diphenylated indans.

Introduction

Intramolecular Friedel-Crafts alkylation and acylation reactions (called cyclialkylation and cycliacylation) offer one of the most facile and versatile pathways for the synthesis of polyalicycles¹. In this paper, we introduce our results on the synthesis of some diphenylindans through new cyclialkylation experiments involving suitably designed alkylation substrates.

Results and discussion

Production of cis-and/or trans-1,2-diphenylindan (7) :

Scheme 1

This was achieved with 1,2,3-triphenyl-1-propanol (**1**), 1,2,3-triphenyl-2-propanol (**2**) and 1-chloro-2,3,3-triphenylpropane (**3**). Informations relating to these three interrelated substrates are given in Scheme 1 and Table 1. The steps in Scheme 1 illustrate that ultimate carbocation **5** is produced directly from **1** (i.e. **1** \rightarrow **5**), via 1,2-hydride shift from **2** (i.e. **2** \rightarrow **6** \rightarrow **5**) and via $\text{Ar}_{1,4}$ assisted ionisation concurrent with 1,3-phenide migration from **3** (i.e. **3** \rightarrow **4** \rightarrow **5**). The latter assumption is well established and has numerous literature precedences². It is here applied to avoid the intermediacy of primary carbocation **4a** which

Table 1. Conditions and results of cyclialkylation reactions^{a,b}

Sl. no.	Substrate	Catalyst type	Solvent	Time (h)	Yield (%)	Production composition (%)
1.	1	AlCl ₃ /CH ₃ NO ₂	PE ^c	3	81	<i>trans</i> -7 (100)
2.	1	85% H ₂ SO ₄	PE	12	89	<i>cis</i> -7 (100)
3.	2	AlCl ₃ /CH ₃ NO ₂	PE	2	84	<i>trans</i> -7 (100)
4.	2	AlCl ₃ /CH ₃ NO ₂	PhH	2	82	<i>cis</i> -7 (47), <i>trans</i> -7 (53)
5.	2	85% H ₂ SO ₄	PE	2	78	8 (100)
6.	2	85% H ₂ SO ₄	PhH	2	83	8 (100)
7. ^d	2	85% H ₂ SO ₄	PhH	13	80	8 (100)
8. ^e	3	AlCl ₃	PhH	1	85	<i>cis</i> -7 (100)
9.	9	AlCl ₃ /CH ₃ NO ₂	PE	2	82	10 (100)
10.	9	AlCl ₃ /CH ₃ NO ₂	PhH	2	87	10 (100)
11.	9	85% H ₂ SO ₄	PE	2	91	10 (33), 11 (67)
12.	9	85% H ₂ SO ₄	PhH	5	89	10 (48), 11 (52)
13. ^d	9	85% H ₂ SO ₄	PhH	10	93	10 (86), 11 (14)
14.	12	AlCl ₃ /CH ₃ NO ₂	PE	5	72	13a (69), 13b (31)
15.	12	85% H ₂ SO ₄	PE	18	80	13a (78), 13b (22)
16.	14	AlCl ₃ /CH ₃ NO ₂	CH ₂ Cl ₂	2	84	15 (100)
17.	14	AlCl ₃ /CH ₃ NO ₂	PhH	8	81	15 (100)
18.	14	85% H ₂ SO ₄	CH ₂ Cl ₂	2	90	15 (100)
19.	14	85% H ₂ SO ₄	PhH	24	91	15 (100)
20. ^f	14	H ₃ PO ₄	–	1	77	15 (100)
21. ^g	14	PPA	–	1	89	15 (100)
22.	16	AlCl ₃ /CH ₃ NO ₂	PE	2	81	17 (100)
23.	16	85% H ₂ SO ₄	PE	2	78	17 (100)

^aUnless specified otherwise, all reactions were conducted at room temperature.

^bWith AlCl₃/CH₃NO₂ catalyst reactant proportions were : carbinol (0.002 mol), AlCl₃ (0.0024 mol), CH₃NO₂ (0.024 mol), solvent (10 ml/g); with 85% H₂SO₄ catalyst proportions were : carbinol (0.002 mol), 85% H₂SO₄ (2 ml), solvent (10 ml/g).

^cPetroleum ether b.p. 60–80°. ^dReaction temperature 50°.

^eReactant proportion was : chloride (0.002 mol), AlCl₃ (0.0002 mol), benzene (0.02 mol). ^fReaction temperature was 230–240°.

^gReaction temperature was 160°.

is not only energetically unfavourable but also because of its known inability to ring close to indans^{1a}. Moreover, the data in Table 1 (Sl. nos. 1–8) reveals that the stereochemical course of the closure step is highly dependent on catalyst type, solvent and structure of starting substrate. While AlCl₃/CH₃NO₂ favoured *trans*

closure, both AlCl₃ and H₂SO₄ favoured *cis* closure. The failure of H₂SO₄ to induce closure of **2** is probably due to the greater tendency under these conditions to localise the +ve charge on the tertiary benzylic center; so elimination to (*E*)-1,2,3-triphenylpropane **8** was favoured. Support for the later explanation could be found in the reported:

Scheme 2

Scheme 3

Scheme 4

closure of $\text{PhCH}_2\text{C}(\text{OH})(\text{CH}_3)\text{CH}_2\text{Ph}$ (where Ph is replaced by CH_3) to 2-methyl-1-phenylindan under comparable conditions³.

Production of *trans*-2-benzyl-1-phenylindan (10)⁴ : This was obtained as sole stereoisomer by cyclialkylating 2-benzyl-1,3-diphenyl-2-propanol (9) in the presence of $\text{AlCl}_3/\text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2$ catalyst. With $85\% \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$ catalyst however, varying proportions of 10 and 2-benzyl-1,3-diphenylpropene (11) were obtained. The sole formation of the *trans* isomer could be rationalised on steric grounds as the *cis* isomer will be more congested. The results are presented in Scheme 2 and Table 1 (Sl. nos. 9–13).

Production of isomeric *r*-1-methyl-1,3-diphenylindan (13a) and *r*-1-methyl-1,c-3-diphenylindan (13b) : A mixture of those two isomers was obtained by cyclialkylating 2,3,4-triphenyl-2-butanol (12) using both $\text{AlCl}_3/\text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2$ and $85\% \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$ catalysts. The results are presented in Scheme 3 and Table 1 (Sl. nos. 14, 15).

Production of *trans*-1,1-dimethyl-3,4-diphenylindan (15) : This was obtained as a sole stereoisomer by cyclialkylating 2-methyl-3,4,4-triphenyl-2-butanol (14) using $\text{AlCl}_3/\text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2$, $85\% \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$, H_3PO_4 and polyphosphoric acid (PPA) catalysts and a variety of reaction conditions. The *trans* identity of this isomer was based on both steric factors and spectral ^1H NMR data where the large *J* value (11.5 Hz) suggests *trans* coupling between the two protons at 2- and 3-positions. The results are shown in Scheme 4 and Table 1 (Sl. nos. 16–21).

Production of *r*-1-ethyl-1,c-3-diphenylindan (17) : This was produced as sole stereoisomer by cyclialkylating 1,1,3-

triphenyl-3-pentanol (16) in the presence of either $\text{AlCl}_3/\text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2$ or H_2SO_4 catalysts. Steric factors suggests this to be the less hindered *r*-1-ethyl-1,c-3-diphenylindan isomer. The results are presented in Scheme 5 and Table 1 (Sl. nos. 22, 23).

Experimental

The instruments and techniques were similar to those reported in our previous paper⁵. Unless otherwise specified the ^1H NMR spectra were performed using the 60 MHz instrument.

Synthesis of starting substrates :

1,2,3-Triphenyl-1-propanol (1) : This was prepared by the reduction of 1,2,3-triphenyl-1-propanone⁶ with LiAlH_4 following standard procedures : white needles from PE ($60\text{--}80^\circ$) (78% yield), m.p. 86° (lit.⁷ m.p. 87°); IR (KBr) ν_{max} 3350, 1590, 1500, 1435, 1365, 1160, 1100, 1060, 750, 695 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 1.9 (s, 1, OH exchangeable with D_2O), 2.8–3.4 (apparent m with strong signal at 3, 3, C^2H , C^3H_2), 4.9 (d, 1, *J* 7.8 Hz, C^1H) and 6.9–7.5 ppm (m, 15, ArH).

1,2,3-Triphenyl-2-propanol (2) : This was prepared by the reaction of dibenzyl ketone with phenylmagnesium bromide. The reaction mixture was left to stir for overnight then decomposed with aq. NH_4Cl solution and the product was extracted as usual. Crystallisation from PE (b.p. $60\text{--}80^\circ$) gave the product as white needles (70%), m.p. 91° (lit.⁸ m.p. $86\text{--}87^\circ$ and $91\text{--}92^\circ$); IR (KBr) ν_{max} 3550, 3010, 2980, 1590, 1480, 1420, 1318, 1160, 1055, 1000, 743, 695 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 1.95 (s, 1, OH exchangeable

Scheme 5

with D₂O), 3.1–3.5 (second order two-spin AB system, due to hindered rotation, consisting of four lines, the inner peaks of which are more intense, 4, 2CH₂) and 7.0–7.5 ppm (m, 15, ArH).

1-Chloro-2,3,3-triphenylpropane (3) : 2,3,3-Triphenyl-1-propanol⁹ obtained by a series of standard steps was converted to **3** by reaction with thionyl chloride in pyridine¹⁰. As usual extraction and crystallisation from PE (40–60°) gave the product as white crystals (76%), m.p. 81°; IR (KBr) ν_{\max} 3080, 2960, 1590, 1480, 1440, 965, 755 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 3.45–3.9 (m, 1, CH), 3.65 (d, 2, CH₂Cl), 3.45–3.9 (d, 1, *J* 10.5 Hz (Ph)₂CH) and 6.9–7.4 ppm (m, 15, ArH) (Found : C, 82.4; H, 6.32; Cl, 11.05. Calcd. for C₂₁H₁₉Cl : C, 82.21; H, 6.19; Cl 11.15%).

2-Benzyl-1,3-diphenyl-2-propanol (9) : Addition of two equivalents of benzylmagnesium chloride to ethyl phenylacetate following reported procedure¹¹ gave **9** as white needles from PE 60–80° (88%), m.p. 115° (lit.¹¹ m.p. 114–115°); IR (KBr) ν_{\max} 3550(s), 3010(s), 2985(s), 1593(s), 1576(w), 1480(s), 1440(s), 1335(m), 1180(s), 1080(s), 1035(s), 740(s), 697(s) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR δ (CDCl₃) δ 1.5 (s, 1, OH exchangeable with D₂O), 2.85 (s, 6, 3CH₂) and 7.45 ppm (s, 15, ArH).

2,3,4-Triphenyl-2-butanol (12) : This was prepared by the addition of a dry benzene solution of 1,2,3-triphenyl-1-propanone⁶ to MeMgI followed by reflux for 1 h and stirring at rt for overnight. Decomposition by sat. aq. NH₄Cl solution, extraction and purification by FC (basic alumina, PE 60–80°/ethyl acetate) gave **12** as pale viscous oil, n_D^{25} 1.5117; IR (film) ν_{\max} 3350(s), 3030(m), 2980(m), 1590(s), 1480(s), 1440(s), 1240(s), 1190(s), 1140(s), 1060(s), 760(s), 690(s) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 1.55 (s, 3, CH₃), 1.95 (s, 1, OH exchangeable with D₂O), 2.8–3.6 (unresolved m, 3, PhCH₂CH) and 7–7.9 ppm (m, 15, ArH) (Found : C, 87.13; H, 7.42. Calcd. for C₂₂H₂₂O : C, 87.41; H, 7.28%).

2-Methyl-3,4,4-triphenyl-2-butanol (14) : Addition of two equivalents of CH₃MgI to a dry benzene solution of methyl 2,3,3-triphenylpropanoate followed by stirring for overnight and decomposition by sat. aq. NH₄Cl solution gave **14** in the form of white crystals PE 60–80° (74%), m.p. 92°; IR (KBr) ν_{\max} 3550(m), 3440(m), 3015(s), 2990(s), 1700(s), 1590(s), 1480(s), 1440(s), 1368(m), 1145(s), 735(s), 695(s) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 1.2 (s, 3, CH₃), 1.33 (s, 3, CH₃), 2 (s, 1, OH exchangeable with D₂O), 3.85 (d, 1, *J* 9 Hz, PhCH), 4.6 (d, 1, *J* 9 Hz, (Ph)₂CH) and 6.8–7.6 ppm (m, 15, ArH) (Found : C, 87.49; H, 7.63. Calcd. for C₂₃H₂₄O : C, 87.34; H, 7.59%).

1,1,3-Triphenyl-3-pentanol (16) : This was obtained by the addition of EtMgBr to 1,3,3-triphenyl-1-propanone followed by stirring for overnight and decomposition by sat. aq. NH₄Cl solution. Flash chromatography (FC) of the liquid product (neutral alumina, PE 60–80°) gave **16** in the form of colourless viscous liquid (77%), n_D^{25} 1.6158; IR (film) ν_{\max} 3550(s), 3450(s), 3045(s), 2915(s), 1590(s), 1480(s), 1372(s), 1260(s), 1073(s), 1022(s), 740(s), 693(s) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 0.8 (t, 3, *J* 7.5 Hz, CH₃), 1.6 (s, 1, OH exchangeable with D₂O), 1.8 (q, 3, *J* 7.5, CH₂), 2.7 (d, 2, *J* 6 Hz, CH₂), 3.9 (apparent t, 1, *J* 6 Hz, (Ph)₂CH) and 7–7.4 ppm (t, 15, ArH) (Found : C, 87.3; H, 7.81. Calcd. for C₂₃H₂₄O : C, 87.34; H, 7.59%).

Synthesis of reference samples :

trans-1,2-Diphenylindan (7) : Addition of phenylmagnesium bromide to 2-phenylindanone¹² and treatment as usual gave 1,2-diphenyl-1-indanol in the form of yellow viscous oil (80%) n_D^{25} 1.6138; IR (film) ν_{\max} 3540(s), 3040(s), 2980(s), 1595(s), 1520(s), 1480(m), 1440(s), 1370(m), 1040(s), 733(s), 692(s) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 3.3–4.1 (m, 3, CH-CH₂), 3.1 (s, 1, OH exchangeable with D₂O) and 7.1–7.8 ppm (m, 14, ArH).

Reduction by P/HI¹³ and recrystallisation from cyclohexane/benzene (4 : 1) gave **7** (72%) as yellow powder, m.p. 123° (lit.¹⁴ m.p. 123–124°); IR (KBr) ν_{\max} 3050(s), 2983(s), 1680(s), 1592(s), 1580(w), 1483(s), 1440(s), 1065(s), 1020(s), 750(s), 695(s) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 3.5 (apparent m, 2, *J* 8.56 Hz, CH₂), 4.13 (m, 1, *J* 8.56 Hz, PhC²H), 4.39 (d, 1, *J* 8.56 Hz, (Ph)₂CH) and 6.5–7.05 ppm (m, 14, ArH); MS *m/z* (%), 270 (M⁺, 58.3), 269 (M⁺-H, 2.2), 191 (M⁺-Ph-2H, 24.7), 179 (M⁺-PhCH-H, 100), 166 ((Ph)₂CH, 6.6), 91 (63.7), 77 (46.3).

(E)-1,2,3-Triphenyl-1-propene (8) : Dehydration of 1,2,3-triphenyl-2-propanol (**2**) by KHSO₄ as reported¹⁵ gave **8** as white crystals from methanol (88%), m.p. 65° (lit.¹⁶ m.p. 63–64°); IR (KBr) ν_{\max} 3060(s), 3010(s), 2980(s), 1590(s), 1570(w), 1480(s), 1422(s), 1285(s), 1070(s), 1020(s), 940(s), 750(s), 693(s) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) δ 4.12 (s, 2, CH₂), 7.1 (s, 1, CH) and 7–7.5 ppm (m, 15, ArH); MS *m/z* (%) 270 (M⁺, 76), 269 (M⁺-H, 29.4), 178 (M⁺-PhCH₂-H, 100), 91 (PhCH₂, 71.4), 77 (23.7).

2-Benzyl-1,3-diphenyl-1-propene (11) : Dehydration of 2-benzyl-1,3-diphenyl-2-propanol (**9**) by AcOH/conc. H₂SO₄¹⁶ and purification by FC (neutral alumina/*n*-hexane) gave **11** (80%) as yellowish oil, n_D^{25} 1.5887 (lit.¹⁶ 1.5930); IR (film) ν_{\max} 3070(s), 3015(s), 2980(s), 1590(s), 1535(w), 1480(s), 1420(s), 1290(m), 1067(s), 1023(s),

960(s), 740(s), 697(s) cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ 3.2 (s, 2, CH_2), 3.4 (s, 2, CH_2), 6.4 (s, 1, CH) and 7.1 ppm (s, 15, ArH); MS m/z (%) 284 (M^+ , 63.4), 207 (M^+ -Ph, 5), 192 (M^+ - PhCH_2 -H, 34.2), 114 (M^+ -Ph CH_2 -Ph-2H, 87.2), 91 (PhCH_2 , 100), 77 (8.2).

Cyclialkylation procedures :

The cyclialkylation procedures reported in earlier papers^{17a,b} were essentially followed. The conditions and results are depicted in Table 1.

Product separation and identification :

cis- and trans-1,2-Diphenylindans (7) : These were separated by column chromatography (CC) using neutral alumina and *n*-hexane/AcOEt. The *trans*-isomer was identical in all respects with the prepared sample : m.p. 122° (lit.¹⁴ m.p. 123–124.5°); IR (KBr) ν_{max} 3050(s), 2983(s), 1680(s), 1592(s), 1580(w), 1483(s), 1440(s), 1065(s), 1020(s), 750(s), 695(s) cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz) δ 3.57–3.64 (m, 2, CH_2), 4.12–4.26 (m, 1, C^1H), 4.39 (d, J 9.5 Hz, 1, C^2H) and 6.57–7.53 ppm (m, 14, ArH); MS m/z (%) 270 (M^+ , 58.3), 269 (M^+ -H, 2.2), 191 (M^+ -Ph-2H, 24.7), 179 (M^+ -PhCH-H, 100), 166 (Ph_2CH , 6.6), 91 (63.7), 77 (46.3) (Found : C, 93.42; H, 6.95. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{18}$: C, 93.33; H, 6.66%). The large J value confirms the *trans*-orientation of this isomer. Again, the distereotopic nature of CH_2 accounts for the multiplicity of the signals.

The *cis*-isomer showed the following properties : m.p. 89°; IR (KBr) ν_{max} 3050(s), 2983(s), 1660(s), 1592(s), 1580(w), 1483(s), 1440(s), 1065(s), 1020(s), 750(s), 695(s) cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ 3.1–3.7 (m, 1, CH_2), 3.7–4.2 (m, 1, C^2H), 4.3 (d, J 5 Hz, 1, C^1H) and 6.7–8.1 ppm (m, 14, ArH); MS m/z (%) 270 (M^+ , 16.9), 269 (M^+ -H, 78), 191 (M^+ -Ph-2H, 74.6), 177 (M^+ -PhCH-3H, 100), 166 ($(\text{Ph})_2\text{CH}$, 96), 91 (8.1), 90 (83.8), 77 (9.3) (Found : C, 93.51; H, 6.45. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{18}$: C, 93.33; H, 6.66%). The smaller J value confirms the *cis*-orientation of this isomer.

(E)-1,2,3-Triphenylpropene (8) : This was identical with our authentic sample : white crystals from methanol m.p. 65° (lit.¹⁵ m.p. 63–64°); IR (KBr) ν_{max} 3060(s), 3010(s), 2980(s), 1590(s), 1570(w), 1480(s), 1422(s), 1285(s), 1070(s), 1020(s), 940(s), 750(s), 693(s) cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz) δ 4.12 (s, 2, CH_2), 7.1 (s, 1, CH) and 7–7.5 ppm (m, 15, ArH); MS m/z (%) 270 (M^+ , 76), 269 (M^+ -H, 29.4), 178 (M^+ -Ph CH_2 -H, 100), 91 (PhCH_2 , 71.4), 77 (23.7).

trans-2-Benzyl-1-phenylindan (10) and 2-benzyl-1,3-diphenylpropene (11) : These were separated by preparative TLC (*n*-hexane/AcOEt, 9.7 : 0.3).

Compound 10 : m.p. 72° (lit.¹⁶ 73.5°); IR (KBr) ν_{max} 3020(s), 2880(s), 1590(m), 1580(m), 1548(w), 1477(s), 1440(s), 1075(s), 1020(s), 740(s), 693(s) cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz) δ 2.74–2.81 (m, 3, PhCH_2CH), 3.03–3.10 (m, 2, C^3H_2), 4.08 (d, J 7.3 Hz, 1, C^1H) and 6.96–7.43 ppm (m, 14, ArH); MS m/z (%) 284 (M^+ , 9.9), 283 (M^+ -H, 23.8), 206 (M^+ -Ph-H, 4.9), 192 (M^+ -Ph CH_2 -H, 100), 165 ($(\text{Ph})_2\text{CH}$, 1.5), 104 (PhCH_2CH , 3), 91 (21.5) (Found : C, 93.1; H, 6.89. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{20}$: C, 92.95; H, 7.04%).

Alkene 11 : Yellowish oil identical in all respects with the prepared authentic sample.

r-1-Methyl-1-1,t-3-diphenylindan (13a) and r-1-methyl-1,c-3-diphenylindan (13b) : These two isomers were separated by CC (neutral alumina, *n*-hexane/benzene, 9 : 1). Isomer **13a** showed the following properties : viscous oil, IR (film) ν_{max} 3050(vw) 2990(w), 1640(s), 1540(w), 1430(m), 1043(s), 720(s) cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ 1.1 (s, 3, CH_3), 2.9–3.5 (m, 2, CH_2), 3.75 (apparent t, J 6 Hz, 1, C^2H) and 6.7–7.4 ppm (m, 14, ArH); MS m/z (%) 283 (M^+ -H, 68.8), 268 (M^+ -H- CH_3 , 26.5), 192 (M^+ - CH_3 -Ph, 100), 177 (72), 115 (34.9), 91 (43.4), 77 (11.9), 65 (6.7), 51 (5.6).

Isomer 13b showed the following properties : viscous oil; IR, MS almost similar to those of **13a**, $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ 1.2 (s, 3, CH_3), 2.9–3.6 (m, 2, CH_2), 3.65 (apparent t, J 6 Hz, 1, C^2H) and 6.7–7.3 ppm (m, 14, ArH). The noted differences in the δ values justifies the choice between the two isomers.

trans-1,1-Dimethyl-2,3-diphenylindan (15) : Crystallisation from petroleum ether (60–80°) afforded the product in the form of white rhombic crystals : m.p. 135°; IR (KBr) ν_{max} 3030(s), 2950(s), 1580(s), 1480(s), 1440(s), 1060(s), 1020(s), 760(s), 695(s) cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz) δ 0.95 (s, 3, CH_3), 1.46 (s, 3, CH_3), 3.4 (d, J 11.5 Hz, 1, C^2H), 4.78 (d, J 11.5 Hz, 1, C^3H) and 7.19–7.34 ppm (m, 14, ArH) (Found : C, 92.73; H, 7.27. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{22}$: C, 92.61; H, 7.38%).

r-1-Ethyl-1,c-3-diphenylindan (17) : This was obtained in the form of white solid from methanol m.p. 83°; IR (KBr) ν_{max} 3100(w), 2965(w), 1634(m), 1596(m), 1487(s), 1446(s), 1375(w), 752(s), 697(s) cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ 0.85 (apparent t, J 7.5 Hz, 3, CH_3), 1.9–2.6 (m, 2, CH_2), 2.6–3.1 (m, 2, C^2H_2), 4.1–4.6 (m, 1, C^3H)

and 6.7–8.0 ppm (m, 14, ArH); MS *m/z* (%) 298 (M^+ , 43), 283 (M^+ -CH₃, 20.3), 269 (M^+ -CH₂CH₃, 100), 221 (M^+ -Ph, 6.1), 128 (M^+ -Ph-CH₂CH₃, 17.8), 91 (PhCH₂, 84.8), 77 (Ph, 33.5) (Found : C, 92.35; H, 7.56. Calcd. for C₂₃H₂₂ : C, 92.61; H, 7.38%).

Commenting on the ¹H NMR spectrum, it is to be noted that the multiplicity of the signals is due to the diastereotopic nature of the two methylene groups of the molecule.

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